

World Safety Journal

A peer-reviewed journal,
published by the World Safety Organization

Journal Homepage:
<https://worldsafety.org/wso-world-safety-journal/>

The economic cost of road traffic accidents in Lebanon

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KEYWORDS

Road Traffic Accidents
Accident Cost
Willingness-to-pay
Human Capital
Lebanon

ABSTRACT

Although it is estimated that more than 1,000 people are killed in road traffic accidents in Lebanon each year, only about 500 people are documented to have died as a result. The continued economic cost of the rising number of traffic accidents is significant and accounts for between 3.2 and 4.8 percent of Lebanon's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Unfortunately, no laws or regulations exist in Lebanon to separate and protect the most vulnerable road users, such as pedestrians and motorcyclists, who suffer disproportionately in traffic accidents and account for 30 to 40% of all fatalities on the road. Although Lebanon has introduced a number of tested best practices for driving safety, many of them are not consistently enforced. For instance, about 15% of front seat passengers are listed as wearing seat belts.

This paper's primary objective is to quantify the cost of road traffic accidents in Lebanon. For estimation, two methods are used: (1) the willingness to pay (WTP) approach, which values society's willingness to pay for avoiding death, injury, and damage outcomes from road crashes; and (2) the human capital (HC) approach, which evaluates the economic loss based on the expense relative to a person's injury, lost income, and property damage.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is estimated that around 1.3 million people lose their lives as a direct result of automobile accidents every year. Between 20 and 50 million additional people experience injuries that do not result in death, with many of these people developing a disability as a direct result of road accidents. Individuals, families, and nations suffer significant financial losses as a result of these accidents; the losses are the result of the cost of treatment, lost productivity for individuals who have been rendered unable to work as a result of injuries, and the time taken off by family members to care for those who have been hurt. According to the World Health Organization, countries lose about 3% of their gross domestic product due to traffic accidents (WHO).

According to recent public health statistics in the MENA region (Middle East and North Africa), the leading cause of death among young adults is car accidents. In terms of socioeconomic measures, such as accident fatality rates, healthy years of life lost due to accidents, and percentage of GDP lost, MENA

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countries are now among the world's worst performers (Dahdah and Bose, 2013). This is due to a mix of risk factors, including excessive speeding coupled with a lack of police enforcement and an inadequate punishment system; rapid motorization expansion, and road construction coupled with inadequate road design.

Since the civil war (1975–1990), Lebanon, a MENA country, has lacked an efficient transportation infrastructure, resulting in a high reliance on private car use, which has exacerbated road traffic congestion, especially in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA), where half of the population lives, making the daily commute to Beirut's city center an ordeal for many people. In addition, the situation has worsened in recent years as a result of the movement of 1.5 million Syrian refugees, who now make up around 25% of Lebanon's permanent population; this has led to a 15–25% increase in road traffic. Lebanon's high reliance on private cars, which is rapidly becoming a transportation nightmare, not only causes severe road traffic congestion, especially during peak hours, but also has significant environmental consequences in terms of noise and air pollution, as well as economic consequences for the country. According to studies conducted for the Ministry of Environment, the cost of urban road traffic congestion in the Greater Beirut Area (GBA) is 8-10% of Lebanon's gross domestic product (Kadi, 2016). In terms of road accidents, the situation in Lebanon is exacerbated by the fact that 30-40% of fatalities involve vulnerable road users, such as pedestrians and motorcyclists.

Lebanon's road safety record is among the worst in the world. Unfortunately, Lebanon's cash-strapped government does not prioritize road safety. The lack of safety features in most automobiles is the leading cause of fatalities on the road. Despite the fact that accidents involving safety-equipped vehicles result in significantly fewer fatalities, Lebanon has no law mandating safety features such as backseat head rests (to prevent neck or back injuries), air bags, anti-lock braking systems (ABS), and electronic stability programs (ESP) to control skids, which are standard and, in some cases, required in the United States and parts of Europe. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), over 1,000 people (adjusted number of deaths) are killed and over 10,000 are injured annually on Lebanon's roadways (see Table 1). Noteworthy is that the mortality rate in Lebanon is higher than the comparable rates in countries of Europe and the USA (see Table 2).

The majority of automobiles in Lebanon are potentially hazardous due to worn-out tires, brakes, and shock absorbers, as well as the absence of safety equipment. Although Lebanon has an annual system for certifying the roadworthiness of automobiles, there are no regulations barring the entry of junk cars from Europe, where they are illegal to drive. These European automobiles with tens of thousands of kilometers on the odometer are altered and sold as "used" in countries with lax regulations, such as Lebanon.

Inexperienced and irresponsible motorists complete the lethal equation. Obtaining a driver's license in Lebanon requires more bureaucratic skills than driving aptitude, and it is not indicative of a driver's skill. Those who can afford to pay baksheesh (under-the-table bribes) are known to send factotums to get licenses in their place. Using a cell phone, eating, drinking, and exchanging money (for passengers in commercial vehicles) are common while driving. On a private motorcycle, the children are pushed between their father, who is perched on the gas tank, and their mother, who is normally positioned sidesaddle on the back rack with another child in her arms. Helmets and seatbelts are required for drivers and people sitting in the front seats of cars (but not for people sitting in the back seats), but these rules are rarely followed, just like speed limits (Choueiri et al., 2015).

Lebanese legislation set speed limits on urban roads nationally at 100 km/h and allowed local authorities to set lower limits. However, enforcement of speed limits is only effective at a rate of 4 to 10, which is low but much more effective than the enforcement of the drink-driving law. The legal

limit for the latter is set at 0.05g/dl but barely has any efficacy when it comes to enforcement. Random breath testing and/or police checkpoints are occasionally set up, but there is no tracking of data related to road deaths caused by alcohol consumption. The seat-belt wearing rate remains low; according to the Lebanese Internal Security Forces, only 15% of the population buckles up. Enforcement effectiveness scores low too. On the other hand, Lebanon has not yet introduced a child restraint law. As for helmet wearing rates, no data is available. Despite a motorcycle helmet law, helmet standards are not mandated and weakly enforced (Choueiri et al., 2015).

This paper's primary objective is to quantify the cost of road traffic accidents in Lebanon. For estimating, two methods are used: (1) the willingness to pay (WTP) approach, which measures how much people are willing to pay to avoid death, injury, and damage from car accidents; and (2) the human capital (HC) approach, which figures out the economic loss based on the cost of treating the person's injury, lost income, and property damage.

Table 1. Road safety in the Middle East: number of deaths and road mortality rate

Ranking	Country	Reported number of deaths	Adjusted number of deaths	Mortality rate 2015
1	Jordan	768	1 913	25.1
2	Saudi Arabia	7 661	7 898	25
3	Oman	913	924	20.57
4	Yemen	3 239	5 248	19.55
5	Iraq	5 789	6 826	18.74
6	Lebanon	630	1 088	18.59
7	Kuwait	473	629	16.16
8	Qatar	204	330	14.76
9	Egypt	8 701	10 466	11.43
10	United Arab Emirates	651	1 021	11.14
11	Bahrain	83	107	7.77

Source: World Road Safety Report, World Health Organization (WHO), International Organization of Motor Vehicle Manufacturers (OICA)

Table 2. Road safety in the rest of the World: number of deaths and road mortality rate

Ranking	Country	Reported number of deaths	Adjusted number of deaths	Mortality rate 2015
1	Brazil	41 059	46 935	22.58
2	Russia	27 025	27 025	18.75
3	Chile	2 108	2 179	12.14
4	Mexico	17 139	15 062	11.85
5	United States	32 719	35 092	10.91
6	Greece	865	1013	9.35
7	Croatia	368	395	9.35

Table 2 (cont.). Road safety in the rest of the World: number of deaths and road mortality rate

Ranking	Country	Reported number of deaths	Adjusted number of deaths	Mortality rate 2015
8	Turkey	4 786	6 687	8.5
9	Czech Republic	654	708	6.7
10	Belgium	724	732	6.48
11	New Zealand	253	272	5.9
12	Slovenia	125	120	5.81
13	Canada	2 077	2 114	5.8
14	Portugal	637	593	5.73
15	Italy	3 385	3 428	5.63
16	Australia	1 192	1 252	5.2
17	France	3 268	3 461	5.18
18	Germany	3 339	3 540	4.34
19	Spain	1 680	1 689	3.6
20	Switzerland	269	269	3.24
21	Netherlands	570	531	3.13
22	Denmark	191	178	3.1
23	United Kingdom	1 770	1 806	2.77
24	Sweden	260	272	2.7

Source: World Road Safety Report, World Health Organization (WHO), International Organization of Motor Vehicle Manufacturers (OICA)

2. QUANTIFYING THE COST OF TRAFFIC ACCIDENTS IN LEBANON

To be able to quantify the overall cost of road traffic accidents in Lebanon or to determine the unit costs, i.e. cost per casualty, from aggregate cost data, it was important to obtain detailed information on road traffic accidents. Unfortunately, previous studies revealed significant underreporting issues concerning road accidents. Underreporting is caused by both definitional inconsistencies and the failure to report some accidents (Choueiri et al., 2015).

2.1 Definition of Road Fatality

According to the Vienna Convention on Road Traffic (Vienna, 1968), a person killed in a road accident is defined as "any individual who was killed outright or died within 30 days as a result of the accident" (UN, Treaty Collection). The Lebanese definition is: "A fatality originating from a traffic accident that occurs either on the spot or while the injured individual is being treated in a hospital for the accident's damage, regardless of how long he or she is hospitalized before dying." As long as the injured person is still in the hospital, there is no precise number of days between injury and death.

If hospital information is included in accident statistics, then the statistics include people who die within 30 days or more, if they die at the hospital. Hospitals, on the other hand, do not report all fatalities to the Traffic Emergency Committee (TEC) at the Internal Security Forces (ISF), despite several efforts to increase this reporting. TEC records nearly as many fatalities as private crash investigators (PCI), who do not have access to hospital records. If only fatalities on the spot, or victims who die within 24 hours are included, then international practice suggests an increase in the number of recorded fatalities; for instance, the World Bank applies a multiplication factor of 1.9 (The World Bank: Lebanon’s Road Safety country Profile).

Noteworthy is that a road injury in Lebanon is defined as a physical harm caused by an accident, whether treated in a hospital or at the scene by rescue teams (Red Cross) in the presence of an inspecting officer. This concept is further broken down into serious and minor injuries. The Lebanese definition of "serious injury" is similar to that of many other countries (Belgium, Canada, Germany, Luxembourg, Spain, and so forth); it is an injury that places the afflicted person's life in jeopardy and necessitates hospitalization for more than 24 hours. It cannot be handled by rescuers or hospital emergency rooms, whose responsibility is confined to keeping the injured individual alive until professional medical personnel arrive. A minor injury is described as one that may be treated on the spot by rescuers or at a hospital's emergency room. It is also an injury that does not require more than 24 hours of hospitalization before the patient can leave the hospital or the medical facility.

2.2 Overview of Possible Sources of Road Accident Information in Lebanon

Road accidents in Lebanon are investigated by the traffic police, who then report the number of victims, fatalities, and injuries to TEC. The phases of the accident cycle are shown in the following figure (Republic of Lebanon, Ministry of Public Works & Transport, 2004).

Figure 1. Phases of the ‘accident cycle’

Typically, the Red Cross takes care of transporting people who have been injured in road accidents; noteworthy is that 80% of all injured people in Lebanon are catered for by the Red Cross. With respect to road fatalities, the civil defense usually take charge.

With respect to property damage only accidents, private crash investigators take charge and fill out accident reports, which include specifics, such as the approximate cost of material losses, the culpability associated with the accident, the number of people involved, and so forth. A group called "Syndicate of Lebanese Traffic Experts" (SOTREX) is in charge of accident investigations.

Insurance companies take charge of claims, number of accidents, fatalities and injuries, as well as current and future costs.

2.3 Road Accidents and Underreporting

According to the Lebanese Internal Security Forces' (ISF), the road safety predicament in Lebanon is greatly underestimated due to serious underreporting problems. Underreporting is a problem that exists in every country's accident statistics; the problem of underreporting appears to become more severe if the severity of an accident is diminished. Data on accidents does not differentiate between less serious and more serious injuries; besides, the criteria that different organizations apply are quite varied. Because of this, the way injuries are defined has a big impact on the total number of accidents, and their consequences, reported by different organizations.

2.4 Evaluation of Crash Cost Values

The Human Capital (HC) and Willingness-to-Pay (WTP) methodologies are the two main approaches used in industrialized nations to calculate crash cost values. The HC method calculates the economic loss based on the expense of treating a person's injury, determining lost income and property damage. Costs for pain and suffering brought about by injury or fatality accidents are also regarded in some HC approaches. Even though this is taken into account, it is still believed that this method, which focuses on economic costs, underestimates the real cost of an accident.

The results of surveys asking individuals how much they would be willing to spend to reduce particular types of risk are the foundation of the WTP strategy. As a result, it assesses the value of preventing traffic accidents, or the price society is willing to pay towards safety improvement. Because it more accurately captures the complete social and economic consequences of fatalities and damages, this approach is seen as more conceptually sound, but it also has certain methodological problems (with respect to the development of survey instruments, and the cost of gathering relevant data).

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

3.1 Sample Population

This cross-sectional study was conducted on a representative sample of drivers over 18 years of age. The following equation was used to figure out the minimum number of drivers to survey:

$$N = p * q * (z_{\alpha/2}/d)^2 \quad (1)$$

where:

- N Minimum required sample size
- p Proportion of drivers who respond positively to the survey;
- q Proportion of drivers who respond negatively to the survey (q = 1-p);
- d Permitted error; and
- $z_{\alpha/2}$ Critical "z" value derived from the standard normal distribution table, where the subscript $\alpha/2$ denotes the tail area.

To determine the minimum sample size, "p" and "q" were assumed to be 0.5; the permitted error was taken as 0.05 at a 95% confidence level. As such, the estimated sample size was calculated to be 377 drivers.

3.2 Survey instruments

The survey instrument was a questionnaire that was adapted and adopted for repeated survey of the general population. It consisted of seven categories of questions: (1) **Demographics**, (2) **Driving Practices**, (3) **Driving Experience**, (4) **Driver Opinion**, (5) **Driver Self Evaluation**, (6) **Situational Driver Behavior**, and (7) **Willingness to Pay**. The main purpose of the questionnaire was to gather information on gender, age group, marital status, income level, owned cars, travel to destination, accident involvement, exposure to accidents, severity-related to accidents, and willingness to pay for increased road safety.

3.3 Participants

Drivers who were willing to take part in the study were required to complete a questionnaire that was posted on several social media sites and linked to a Google form so that it could be seen by others. At the end of the survey, only 380 drivers were taken into account, given that drivers who did not answer a good number of questions were left out of further analyses.

4. RESULTS

4.1 driver characteristics

The percentage distribution of the surveyed drivers by gender is displayed in Table 3. The proportion of male and female drivers among the respondents was nearly identical. A chi-square test revealed, at a significance level of 5%, that there was no gender difference among the respondents ($\chi^2(1) = 1.053$, $p = .305$).

Table 3. Frequency and Percent Distribution of Participants according to Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Chi-Square Test	Sig
Male	200	52.6%	1.053	.305
Female	180	47.4%		

More than eighty-six percent of the respondents traveled for business purposes, while the remaining respondents traveled for educational or other purposes (see Table 4). At the 5% level of significance, a chi-square test revealed a significant difference between business and educational/other purposes ($\chi^2(1) = 203.379$, $p < .001$).

Table 4. Frequency and Percent Distribution of Participants according to Travel Reason

Travel Reason	Frequency	Percent	Chi-Square Test	Sig
Business purposes	329	86.6%	203.379	< .001
Educational or other purposes	51	13.4%		

The majority of the respondents were between 18 and 29 years (93.7 percent), followed by those between 30 and 44 years (12 percent) and 45 to 59 years (12 percent). Notably, none of the respondents were 60 years or older (see Table 5). A chi-square test revealed a significant difference between the age groups at the 5% level of significance ($\chi^2(2) = 622.821, p < .001$).

Table 5. Frequency and Percent Distribution of Participants according to Age Group

Age Group	Frequency	Percent	Chi-Square Test	Sig
18 - 29 years	356	93.7%	622.821	< .001
30 - 44 years	12	3.2%		
45 - 59 years	12	3.2%		

The distribution of the respondents according to educational level shows that 86.3 percent possess a university degree or higher, followed by respondents who have completed secondary school (12.6 percent), and 1.1 percent who have completed primary school (see Table 6). The latter is understandable given that education in Lebanon is compulsory until completing the intermediate school cycle, which is accessible to all Lebanese students. Given that the government has no proper control over children who live in urban slums or in remote rural areas, approximately 95 percent of school-age children usually attend schools. At the 5% level of significance, a chi-square test revealed a significant difference in educational level among the respondents ($\chi^2(2) = 487.663, p < .001$).

Table 6. Frequency and Percent Distribution of Participants according to Educational Level

Educational Level	Frequency	Percent	Chi-Square Test	Sig
Elementary	4	1.1%	487.663	< .001
Secondary	48	12.6%		
University Degree or higher	328	86.3%		

As participation in the interview is restricted to those who are at least 18 years old, it is reasonable to assume that the vast majority of those who answer the survey will be married given that young adults in Lebanon are encouraged to marry at a young age (see Table 7). As the table reveals, over sixty-eight percent of the respondents are married. At the 5% level of significance, a chi-square test revealed a significant difference in marital status among the respondents ($\chi^2(3) = 241.16, p < .001$).

Table 7. Frequency and Percent Distribution of Participants according to Marital Status

Marital Status	Frequency	Percent	Chi-Square Test	Sig
Single	93	24.5%	241.16	< .001
Married	260	68.4%		
Divorced	21	5.5%		
Widowed	6	1.6%		

The majority of the respondents, or 62.1%, have annual incomes of less than 1 million Lebanese pounds (approximately \$633 US), followed by respondents with incomes of between 1 and 2 million Lebanese pounds (22.1%), and finally, 15.8% of respondents have annual incomes of more than 2 million Lebanese pounds (see Table 8). These results are consistent with the income levels of the

general population of Lebanon. A chi-square test revealed a significant difference in the respondents' income levels ($\chi^2(2) = 143.832$, $p < .001$).

Table 8. Frequency and Percent Distribution of Participants according to Income Level

Income Level	Frequency	Percent	Chi-Square Test	Sig
Under 1 million L.L.	236	62.1%	143.832	< .001
Between 1 and 2 million L.L.	84	22.1%		
2 million L.L. and over	60	15.8%		

According to the distribution of respondents by number of cars owned, the majority of the respondents (86.4 percent) indicated that they have access to more than one car at their household (see Table 9). This is logical given the limited availability of an efficient public transportation system. A chi-square test revealed a significant difference in the number of owned cars among the respondents at the 5% level of significance ($\chi^2(3) = 278.695$, $p < .001$).

Table 9. Frequency and Percent Distribution of Participants according to Owned Vehicles

Owned cars	Frequency	Percent	Chi-Square Test	Sig
1 car	52	13.7%	278.695	< .001
2 cars	228	60.0%		
3 cars	88	23.2%		
4 cars or more	12	3.2%		

Every day, 27.9 percent of the respondents travel between 10 and 14 kilometers to reach their intended destination, 22.6 percent commute between 15 and 19 kilometers, and 21.6 percent travel between 5 and 9 kilometers (see Table 10). A chi-square test revealed a significant difference in the respondents' daily travel to destination ($\chi^2(4) = 32.0$, $p < .001$).

Table 10. Frequency and Percent Distribution of Participants according to Travel to Destination

Distance to destination	Frequency	Percent	Chi-Square Test	Sig
Less than 5 km	40	10.5%	32.0	< .001
5 - 9 km	82	21.6%		
10 – 14 km	106	27.9%		
15 - 19 km	86	22.6%		
20 km and over	66	17.4%		

The vast majority (75.8 percent) of the respondents reported that at least one member of the family had been involved in an automobile accident (see Table 11). A chi-square test revealed a significant difference between the respondents according to accident involvement at the 5% level of significance ($\chi^2(1) = 101.095$, $p < .001$).

Table 11. Frequency and Percent Distribution of Participants according to Accident Involvement

Accident Involvement	Frequency	Percent	Chi-Square Test	Sig
Yes	288	75.8%	101.095	< .001
No	92	24.2%		

In terms of injury severity, the majority of the respondents (53 percent) stated that either they or someone they know did not sustain injuries in road accidents, while 27.7 percent of the respondents stated that either they or someone they know sustained light injuries, and 9.6 percent of the respondents indicated that either they or someone they know sustained equally medium or serious injuries (see Table 12). A chi-square test revealed that there was a significant difference in severity type among the respondents ($\chi^2(3) = 190.147$, $p < .001$).

Table 12. Frequency and Percent Distribution of Participants according to Severity Type

Severity Type	Frequency	Percent	Chi-Square Test	Sig
Serious injuries	37	9.6%	190.147	< .001
Medium injuries	37	9.6%		
Light injuries	105	27.7%		
No injuries	201	53.0%		

More than 40% of those surveyed stated that they are likely to be involved in a car accident but are not certain. This was followed by over 30 percent who noted that it is likely to get involved but with a medium probability; twenty-three percent of the respondents indicated that it is unlikely that they will be involved in a car accident. Only 4.2% of the respondents noted that it is "probable" or "extremely likely" that they will be involved in a car accident during their lifetime (see Table 13). A chi-square test revealed a significant difference between the respondents according to the degree of exposure to road accidents at the 5% level of significance ($\chi^2(1) = 111.958$, $p < .001$).

Table 13. Frequency and Percent Distribution of Participants according to Accident Exposure

Degree of exposure to road accidents	Frequency	%	Chi-Square Test	Sig
Unlikely to be involved	88	23.2%	111.958	< .001
Likely but with a low probability	156	41.1%		
Likely but with a medium probability	120	31.6%		
Likely but with a high probability	16	4.2%		

4.2 Accident Cost Calculations

During the last two decades, one of the most discussed aspects of monetizing the level of road safety was the development of the so-called 'Value of Statistical Life (VSL)'. Generally, pain, sorrow, and lost quality of life as a consequence of road accidents are regarded in this value. The methods of monetizing can be distinguished by means of approaches like the Human Capital (HC) approach and the Willingness-to-Pay (WTP) approach (Dionne and Lanoie, 2004).

The HC approach deals with the monetary contribution to society, whereas the WTP approach is based on the personal preferences of individuals. People show their willingness either to pay a specific amount of money for the reduction of an accident risk or to accept money for accepting the risk. Depending on the WTP method used, the value is either directly asked for or figured out from choice experiments.

Because the HC method does not provide enough weight to non-market goods, like avoiding pain or sadness, the WTP method is regarded as a good way to figure out the VSL.

4.2.1 Willingness to Pay for Road Safety Improvement

In Lebanon, the real risk of death in traffic accidents is 78 deaths per million people per year (as based on the unadjusted ISF figures); hence, a 50% reduction in risk results in 39 deaths per 1,000,000 people, while a 20% reduction results in 16 deaths per 1,000,000 people.

To ascertain the value of statistical life, the respondents were asked how much financial compensation they would be willing to contribute towards safety risk reductions of 50% and 20%, respectively. The following table summarizes the findings for each risk reduction strategy.

Table 14. Dollars per year for Options A and B

\$/year	Option A (50% risk reduction)	Option B (20% risk reduction)
2.50	24	40
5.00	20	24
10.00	52	44
25.00	28	52
50.00	76	76
75.00	8	20
100.00	64	20
125.00	4	50
150.00	100	48
Total	376	374

The table below provides descriptive statistics of risk reductions.

Table 15. Relevant Descriptive Statistics for Options A and B

Option	N	Mean (\$ per year)	Std. Deviation (\$ per year)	Median (\$ per year)
A (50% risk reduction)	376	73.62	55.93	50
B (20% risk reduction)	374	60.40	52.36	50

Option A (50 percent risk reduction) reduces the annual accident risk by \$73.62, whereas Option B (20 percent risk reduction) reduces the annual accident risk by \$60.40. The median value for both risk reductions is \$50.

Given that the actual risk of death in car accidents in Lebanon is about 78 deaths per million people per year (as based on the unadjusted ISF figures), Option A (50 percent risk reduction) implies that the statistical value of life is:

$$\frac{\$73.61}{\text{year}} \times \frac{1,000,000}{39} = \$1,887,436$$

In the case of Option B (20% risk reduction), the value of statistical life is:

$$\frac{\$60.40}{\text{year}} \times \frac{1,000,000}{16} = \$3,775,000$$

While it is obvious that the respondents were prepared to pay a premium for a reduced safety risk, they were unable to distinguish between low and high risks. As a result, the values for options A and B varied significantly with respect to VOSL.

Table 16. Overall cost of the life loss in dollars per year

Year	Population	Number of road fatalities as per ISF	Average of VOSLs (in dollars) for 20% and 50% risk reduction	Overall cost of the life loss in dollars per year
2007	3,986,852	487	\$2,831,218	\$1,378,803,166
2008	4,111,000	333	\$2,831,218	\$942,795,594
2012	4,337,141	378	\$2,831,218	\$1,070,200,404
2014	5,603,000	537	\$2,831,218	\$1,520,364,066
2015	5,851,479	575	\$2,831,218	\$1,627,950,350
2016	6,006,668	472	\$2,831,218	\$1,336,334,896
Average / year				\$1,312,741,413

However, the amount shown above is the bare minimum because it only considers the number of road fatalities, without reference to serious, medium, minor injuries and property damage only accidents. Studies have shown that a serious injury accounts for 10% of a road fatality; a minor injury accounts for 1% of a road fatality; and a property damage only accounts for 0.1 percent of a road fatality. These percentages are applied in the following table to estimate the overall cost of road accidents in Lebanon.

Table 17. Adopted percentages to determine the overall cost of accidents

Injury Severity	Number (2016)	VOSL in \$	Total Cost
Fatalities	472	\$2,831,218	\$1,336,334,896
Serious injuries (10% of a fatality cost)	594	\$283,122	\$168,174,468
Minor injuries (1% of a fatality cost)	2536	\$28,312	\$71,799,232
Property Damage Only (0.1% of a fatality cost)	21732	\$2,831	\$61,523,292
Total Cost			\$1,637,831,888

Because not all traffic accidents are reported to the police, coupled with problems, such as cover-ups and missing accident reports, the total cost shown above represents the least amount of money associated with road accidents.

It should be noted, without delving into details, that unmarried respondents (who tended to be relatively young) had higher WTP values than married respondents; the reason being is that married respondents typically have a greater responsibility at home in terms of providing support to families. Furthermore, the WTP values decreased with increased age and larger family size; in this respect, younger respondents were found to adopt higher WTP values, as compared to older respondents. It was interesting to note that education, economic standing and distance to destination positively influenced WTP, implying that advanced years of studies and better economic standing were associated with higher WTP values.

4.2.2 Human Capital Cost

The table below summarizes the process of the HC approach adopted in this study to estimate the accident costs (Mofadal and Kanitpong, 2016; Silcock, 2003).

Table 18. Human Capital approach

Cost Component	Estimation Formula
Loss of Productivity	<p>1) Lost productivity in terms of income loss due to fatalities = [No. fatalities × average age in years] × [foregoing income per year using $\sum_{i=1}^N W(1+g)^i / (1+r)^i$].</p> <p>2) Lost productivity in terms of income loss due to serious injury = [No. of serious injuries] × [No. of days in hospital] × [average wage per day].</p> <p>3) Lost productivity in terms of income loss from Middle and slight injuries (during treatment or recovery period) = [No. of Middle injuries] × [No. of days in hospital] × [average wage per day] + [No. of slight injuries] × [No. of days in hospital] × [average wage per day].</p> <p>4) Lost output in terms of income loss due to time lost normally spent by casualties with their families and community in social activities. = [No. fatalities] × [No. of hours per lost years] × [average wage per hour] + [No. of disabilities] × [No. of hours per lost month] × [average wage per hour] + [No. of injuries] × [No. of hours per lost days] × [average wage per hour].</p>
Loss Due to Quality of Life Costs	<p>Total quality of life costs = [No. of fatalities] × [amount compensated by insurance companies] + [No. of injuries] × [amount compensated by insurance companies]</p>
Medical Costs	<p>1) Total medical costs (disabilities) = [No. of disabilities cases with fracture injuries] × [average hospitalization days] × [average hospitalization expenses per/person/day].</p> <p>2) Total medical costs (serious injury) = [No. of serious injury cases] × [average hospitalization days] × [average hospitalization expenses per/person/day].</p> <p>3) Total medical costs (slight injuries) = [No. of slight injury cases] × [average hospitalization days] × [average hospitalization expenses per/person/day]</p>
Vehicle Damage and Detention Costs	<p>1) Total vehicle damage costs = [No. of total vehicles damaged] × [average vehicle damage costs]</p> <p>2) Total vehicle detention costs = [No. of total repaired vehicles (by vehicle type)] × [average vehicle repair period (in days)] × [average vehicle rental cost/day]</p>

The following figures were taken into consideration in determining the final cost:

- **Accident Severity**
 - Serious Injury: \$1494.17
 - Medium Injury: \$1162.35
 - Light Injury: \$720.42
- **Average Annual GDP per Capita**
 - \$6983.7
- **Average Annual Growth Rate**
 - 4.26%
- **Discount rate**
 - 3.5%
- **Average Number of Lost Output Years**
 - 31 years
- **Administrative Costs**
 - 10% to the total cost derived from human and vehicle costs.

As a result, the total cost associated with road accidents and the overall cost derived from the HC approach are shown in the table below.

Cost Category	Estimated Cost in \$US	Percentage	Percentage of Total Cost
Human Costs			
Loss of Productivity	\$1,050,280,531	94.55%	81%
Loss due to Quality of Life Costs	\$30,944,000	2.79%	2%
Medical Costs	\$29,596,760	2.66%	2%
Subtotal	\$1,110,821,291	100%	85%
Vehicle Costs			
Vehicle Damage Costs	\$65,196,000	92%	5.0%
Vehicle Detention Costs	\$5,324,340	8%	0.4%
Subtotal	\$70,520,340	100%	5.4%
General Costs			
Policing Costs			
Court Costs	10% of the total cost	100%	9%
Insurance Costs			
Subtotal	\$118,134,163		
Total Accident Costs	\$1,299,475,794		

As can be deduced from the above table, the HC approach yields an accident cost figure of \$1,299,475,794.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

This study, one of the first on the economic cost of road traffic accidents in Lebanon, reveals that the minimum costs associated with road accidents, as determined by the WTP and HC approaches, are quite high; for example, in 2016, the costs determined by the WTP approach were \$1,637,831,888, while the costs determined by the HC approach were \$1,299,475,794. These figures are based on

unadjusted ISF road fatality and injury statistics. If the World Bank's correction factor of 1.9 is applied (The World Bank: Lebanon's Road Safety Country Profile), then the amounts calculated in this study would nearly double and become comparable to those determined by the World Bank, or \$2,767,000,000 for 2016.

According to the WTP approach, the accident cost rises to \$3,111,880,587.2 (or 6.077 percent of the country's GDP); however, the cost rises to \$2,469,004,008.6 (or 4.821 percent of the country's GDP) according to the HC approach. The average of the two approaches is \$2,790,442,297.9, or 5.449 percent of the Lebanon's GDP, which are very close to the World Bank's figures for 2016 (\$2,767 million and 5.4 percent of the Lebanon's GDP) (The World Bank: The World Bank in Lebanon; The World Bank: Lebanon's Road Safety Country Profile). Despite the availability of statistics on road traffic injuries in Lebanon, underreporting of road traffic deaths and injuries remains a significant concern that prevents an accurate assessment of Lebanon's burden. However, based on the limited data available, road traffic injuries appear to pose a significant threat to national health.

By all means, the accident costs determined in this study are significant in a country like Lebanon, which has been plagued by multiple problems for nearly three years, including an economic and financial crisis, COVID-19, and the August 4, 2020 explosion at the Port of Beirut. The most negative (and longest-lasting) impact has been the economic crisis. According to the World Bank's Spring 2021 Lebanon Economic Monitor (The World Bank: Lebanon Economic Monitor), Lebanon's economic and financial crisis is expected to be one of the top ten, if not the top three, most catastrophic crises to occur since the mid-nineteenth century.

Without a doubt, the economic and financial crisis has had a negative impact on roads, highways, road safety, and motorists. Due to prohibitively expensive spare parts, an increasing number of motorists are finding it difficult to maintain their vehicles, putting themselves and other road users at risk; they no longer have the means to change tires, replace headlights, windshield wipers, brakes, and shock absorbers, etc. Even though Lebanese are well aware of the risks, car maintenance has become less of a priority for those burdened by increasingly exorbitant bills; in order to avoid an unexpected bill, some drivers attempt to extend the life of defective parts for as long as necessary.

In conclusion, a corrupt political Lebanese class, obedient policymakers, and cronies have created unprecedented misery, resulting in an economic, banking, and financial meltdown. Their pervasive corruption, criminal negligence, and incompetence have brought the Horses of the Apocalypse disaster to Lebanon and its people, and road infrastructure and safety. The so-called 'Lebanese politicians and elites' profit from the corrupt system — and foreign donors keep propping them up to hang onto their own influence.

REFERENCES

- Choueiri E.M., Choueiri G.B., and Choueiri B.M. (2015). Road safety in Lebanon: magnitude, cost and potential countermeasures. *Advances in Transportation Studies, Section B* 35, pp. 73-88.
- Dahdah S. and Bose D. (2013). Road traffic injuries: a public health crisis in the Middle East and North Africa. The World Bank, Transport Notes, TRN-45.
- Dionne G. and Lanoie P. (2004). Public Choice about the Value of a Statistical Life for Cost-Benefit Analyses: The Case of Road Safety. *Journal of Transport Economics and Policy, University of Bath*, vol. 38(2), pages 247-274, May.
- Kadi S. (2016). Traffic Congestion Adds to Lebanon's Many Woes. *The Arab Weekly*.
- Mofadal A. and Kanitpong K. (2016). Analysis of Road Traffic Accident Costs in Sudan Using the Human Capital Method. *Open Journal of Civil Engineering*, vol. 6(2), March.

Republic of Lebanon, Ministry of Public Works & Transport (2004). The Cost of Road Traffic Accidents. Technical Report, SIDA Reference No. 2000-04865, May.

Silcock R. (2003). Guidelines for Estimating the Cost of Road Crashes in Developing Countries. Technical Report. Retrieved from:

http://www.transportlinks.org/transport_links/filearea/documentstore/105_R%207780.PDF).

United Nations: Treaty Collection. Convention on Road Traffic. Retrieved from:

https://treaties.un.org/Pages/ViewDetailsIII.aspx?chapter=11&mtdsg_no=XI-B-19&src=TREATY

The World Bank: Lebanon Economic Monitor, Spring 2021: Lebanon Sinking (to the Top 3). Retrieved from:

<https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/lebanon/publication/lebanon-economic-monitor-spring-2021-lebanon-sinking-to-the-top-3>

The World Bank: Lebanon's Road Safety Country Profile. Retrieved from:

<https://www.roadsafetyfacility.org/country/lebanon>

The World Bank: The World Bank in Lebanon. Retrieved from:

<https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/lebanon/overview>

World Health Organization. Retrieved from:

<https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/road-traffic-injuries>

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